

THE NEED TO FORM PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION GRADUATES

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Abstract

This article presents the attitudes, problems and suggestions of both workers and employers to the skill requirements in the new economic conditions. Competency approach is designed to solve existing problems in the educational process that are still not solved in the theory and practice of vocational education technology.

Key words: *competence approach, competence, competence, variability, continuous education*

The dynamics of social development in the current period require a serious review and reassessment of the existing education system. Changes in the technologies of production, economic and social relations during the last decades have created new requirements for human resources. Today, a successful professional and social career of a specialist cannot prepare him to master new technologies, to adapt to new conditions of work, to constantly "raise" his professional level to the level of quality necessary for solving new types of professional tasks.

Undoubtedly, the main task of the vocational education system in modern times can be described as the preparation of graduates-specialists who freely master their profession and can successfully compete in the labor market. In-demand and competitive training involves:

formation of a new content teaching system for the all-round harmonious development of the learner's personality, taking into account the learner's abilities, motivations, valuable orientations, potential opportunities for independent education;

acquisition of high professional knowledge and skills by learners that meet the requirements of the state educational standards of vocational education and the requirements of enterprises that are employer customers;

ensuring the integration of the content of professional education, achieving international standards;

ensuring flexibility, variety and continuity of training;

active approach to the content of educational programs;

formation of high professional competence.

In the new economic conditions, the attitudes of both workers and employers to skill requirements will change: as a result, working professionals will understand the need to study, and employers will understand the need to train.

From the individual's point of view, "Basic education" can no longer guarantee the social protection of workers in market conditions, instead a new approach - "Lifelong learning" is emerging. This is where the need to create a "unified system of lifelong learning" based on unified approaches to the creation of educational content arises.

Fulfillment of these requirements requires large-scale work on changing the teaching process, awareness of the need to introduce innovative approaches by the administration and teachers of the educational institution.

Competency approach is designed to solve existing problems in the educational process that are still not solved in the theory and practice of vocational education technology. The task of education is to actualize the demand for education among learners and to ensure high quality of training of specialists in the developing professional education system. A competent approach is considered to have such possibilities.

At its core, the competent approach assumes that the training of specialists is the acquisition by graduates of the skills and abilities necessary for the successful performance of functions in their future workplaces.

Competence is considered as a person's ability to demonstrate knowledge, professional skills and apply them in non-standard situations, that is, it is a personal factor of the educational process. Competence that enables the implementation of a certain professional activity opens up the possibility of continuing education and ensures the acquisition of new skills and the development of a culture of social behavior.

In the psychological-pedagogical literature, the concepts of "competence" and "competence" are increasingly being used instead of the term "professionalism". Competence includes many other components in addition to technological training, as well as features that every specialist needs to one degree or another these days.

Competence emerges as a leading substantive basis that allows for the formation of the following needs:

rethinking educators' views of learners, as they may all be competent; accordingly, pedagogues need to learn to look at each learner from the point of

view of having a set of unique qualities that are important for success in the field of activity and one or another profession;

in competent teaching, the didactic value of the educational process, the task of personal development through an individual approach to each learner comes to the fore. It is important for the educator to develop approaches that are effective and at the same time interesting for learners;

use of teaching methods that help students to determine and develop their competence depending on their personal inclinations and interests;

radical rejection of traditional measures of student assessment, changing the status of educational textbooks.

The widespread use of the competence approach in education is understood as the desire to emphasize the use of progressive innovative technologies and best methods of teaching. The concept of "innovation" is not only meaningful as "creation and distribution of news", but also as "restructuring, changes in the type of activity, way of thinking" associated with these news. However, using the term "competency approach" in this context can cause confusion for those who do not fully understand what it is. Despite the growing popularity of this concept, there is still no generally accepted definition of it, and no point of reckoning has been found for any of the various approaches to defining and using this term.

The dictionary of foreign words interprets the concept of "competence" as having the right to do or decide something within the scope of one's knowledge or authority, to make a judgment about something.

In the psychological literature, in particular, in the "Practical Dictionary of the Psychologist", the concept of "social-psychological competence" is explained, which is "formed by the individual during the acquisition of communication systems and their inclusion in cooperative activities."

All these definitions have a lot in common, and at the same time, the multifaceted nature of the understanding of competence is evident.

In EU educational practice, "competence" is a general evaluative term and represents the ability to perform activities with "knowledge of the work". It is usually used in relation to persons of a certain socio-professional status, describing the degree of compatibility of their knowledge and skills, their understanding, to the level of complexity of the tasks they perform and the problems they solve.

All recent UNESCO documents and programs focus on quality policy in the field of education, including:

"Lisbon Convention" on the recognition of qualifications related to higher education in the European region (1997);

Document "Education: Hidden Treasure" of the International Commission on Education in the 21st Century, 1997);

"Bologna Declaration" of education ministers of European countries (1999);

International Education Recommendations on Education for All (2000);

Prague Communiqué on Common Quality Methodology and Comparable Benchmarks (2001).

Being competent means being able to mobilize existing knowledge and experiences, one's mood and will to solve problems in concrete life situations. Competence does not lead to the acquisition of knowledge and skills in a certain quantitative ratio, in a concrete volume. At the same time, competence cannot appear without knowledge and experience in the activity. In addition, competence is directly proportional to the conscious attitude and activity of a person towards his education.

Thus, the concept of "competence" is considered integrative, it describes not the elements of the system themselves, but the relationships between them. The specific implementation of this concept depends on the type of situation. Therefore, the main (most universal) competencies are considered to be the result not only of professional education, but also of the educational experiences of a person in general. Their widespread use is fully justified, especially in connection with the need to modernize (update) the educational content.

Researchers-scientists see the differences between a competent specialist and a qualified specialist in the sense that a competent specialist not only has a certain level of knowledge, skills and abilities, but also manages to use them in his work. Competence assumes that an individual has internal motivation to perform his professional activities in a quality manner, has professional values and treats his profession as a value. Competence is the ability of a specialist to go beyond the scope of his profession, he is considered to have some creative potential for self-development. However, the fulfillment of this important scientific and practical task is hindered by contradictions between:

between the theoretical orientation of the training content and personal development of the future specialist;

between the traditional approach to the evaluation of professional training and the emerging market of educational services;

between the requirements for effective diagnostic methods of evaluating the quality of training of specialists in professional educational institutions and the

lack of sufficient scientific and methodological support for ensuring the current and final control of the quality of training;

between the demands placed on the specialist by the labor market and the readiness of teachers to train a competitive graduate-specialist;

between the existing system of evaluation of professional training and orientation of students to evaluate their professional qualities accordingly.

The purpose of vocational education is not only to teach a person to do something, to acquire professional skills, but also to give him the ability to solve situations that arise in various life and professional situations.

Currently, one of the most important tasks in updating professional education is the problem of defining competencies.

One of the ways to achieve professional competence is the development of the student's critical thinking skills, which helps the student to find his priorities, increases the level of culture, develops the ability to analyze the situation, and cultivates independence.

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